

NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION OF ELECTRIC FIELD EFFECTS ON SPRAY JET FLAMES CONTAINING CHARGED DROPLETS

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Abstract

Transition to a zero-carbon transportation sector requires the development of fuel-flexible combustion systems. The use of electrostatic fields offers the possibility to control both fuel mixing and flame characteristics. This study investigates the use of electrostatic fields to control a spray jet flame using charged droplets. The focus of this work is on the effects of an external electric field parallel to the jet direction on the spray penetration and the flame shape and location. This study is conducted using large-eddy simulations under the assumption that charged species generated in the combustion process are negligible. Results show that with practical electrostatic fields and droplet charges achievable with state-of-the-art atomisers, it is possible to significantly change the cold-flow spray penetration. Electric forces in the opposite direction to the spray jet lead to a reduction in the spray penetration, an effect that increases with stronger electrostatic fields. This also leads to an increase in drag forces between the droplets and the air-flow, resulting in a decrease in the penetration of the air jet. The lower penetration of droplets under electrostatic fields leads to a more compact flame in the corresponding reacting cases. Fuel vapour tends to be confined in a region much closer to the jet exit when the applied electric force is in the opposite direction to the jet. Similar trends are also shown by the temperature field and mass fraction of the combustion products. This study suggests that electrostatic fields can provide an element of control over spray jet flames through the use of charged fuel droplets, and provides a basis for future investigations that could lead to the development of novel hybrid thermal-electric combustion systems.

Introduction

An urgent transition to a zero-carbon energy infrastructure is needed to offset the impact of human activities on the concentration of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere and on climate change. Analysing carbon dioxide emissions by sector [1], more than 16% of emissions are from transportation and around 12% of transportation emissions are from aviation. Decarbonising these sectors necessarily requires the use of alternative energy vectors, including batteries and zero-carbon fuels, as well as the development of new technologies for their safe and efficient use. Although huge progress towards a zero-carbon economy has been made for power generation, e.g., through the development of technologies for zero-carbon fuels [2] and land transportation, with electrification being the main solution to abate carbon emissions (e.g., [3]), challenges are still present for the aviation sector. Because of the low energy density of current battery technology, electric propulsion is only viable for short-distance flights. Furthermore, the necessity of keeping the weight and the size of the aircraft low, together with safety considerations, makes the use of zero-carbon fuels such as hydrogen very challenging. It is therefore not surprising that the main manufacturers are currently looking at hybrid thermal-electric propulsion configurations [4] coupled with sustainable aviation fuels (SAFs) as a medium-term solution to lower the carbon footprint of aviation. Hybrid thermal-electric engines imply a large availability of electric energy on board, which could offer new possibilities to achieve control over the combustion process and possibly extend the range of fuels used in aviation. In this context, the development of technologies that make use of electric energy to improve the mixing [5] and combustion characteristics (e.g., [6]) have been proposed.

In general, the behavior of a combustion system used in aviation is very sensitive on the

type of fuel. In most cases, an injection system and a combustor designed to work for a given fuel lose performance (e.g., lower quality atomisation, higher emissions at the exhaust) when operated with fuels with significantly different properties. Consequently, SAFs are typically designed with thermophysical properties that replicate the properties of standard aviation fuel so that they can be used in current combustion technologies. However, this may exclude some fuels that have good properties from an environmental viewpoint because the combustor design is not suitable for their use. From this perspective, it would be ideal to have a combustor that could burn fuels with a wide range of properties, i.e., a combustor that is conceived as fuel-flexible. By taking advantage of the electric energy available on board in hybrid configurations, Fredrich et al. [5] proposed the use of charge-injection atomisation and electrostatic control of droplet trajectory to achieve pre-evaporation of the fuel in compact spaces. Considering the same technology, Giusti and Fredrich [7] further investigated the possibility of pre-evaporating fuels characterised by different properties, such as n-decane, n-heptane and ethanol. Their study concluded that it is possible to control the trajectory of droplets of different fuels and achieve their pre-evaporation with similar electric field strengths. Although the focus of those studies was exclusively on pre-evaporation technologies, such work is an important step towards the development of new fuel-flexible technologies that utilise electric control.

The possibility of using electric control is not limited to the modulation of mixing. Electric fields can also be used to directly affect the flame characteristics. Over the years, there have been many studies, mainly experimental, that have demonstrated that electric fields (both DC and AC) can change the flame shape, the emissions and also allow for the control of combustion instabilities (e.g., [8–11]). The macroscopic effect of electric fields observed in those investigations is mainly due to the ionic wind effect induced by the electric forces acting on charged species. In the context of spray flames with no electric fields, recent studies have also shown that the presence of charged droplets could affect the local flame structure [12]. However, the combination of an electrostatic field and charged droplets in a reacting environment has not been investigated yet. In this case, electrostatic fields are expected to affect both the droplet location, and therefore the formation of a gaseous mixture, and the flame characteristics.

The aim of this work is to investigate the use of electrostatic fields to manipulate the mixing and reactive field in a spray jet flame containing charged droplets, a configuration of practical interest for both power generation and transportation. The specific objectives of this work are (i) to investigate the effect of an electric field parallel to the jet axis on the location of charged droplets in cold flow conditions and (ii) to study the flame characteristics, such as shape and location, for different strengths of the external electric field. The investigation is performed using large-eddy simulations under the assumption of negligible formation of charged species during the combustion process. This assumption allows us to decouple the effects of electric fields on the mixture formation due to the modulation of spray location from the effects on ionic species, therefore providing a first assessment of the impact of spray control on the reacting field.

Methods

Configuration

A spray jet flame, schematically shown in Figure 1, is investigated. The configuration replicates the main characteristics of the piloted spray flame investigated at the University of Sydney (e.g., Ref. [13]). The spray, generated upstream of the burner, is injected together with an air flow by means of a central duct of diameter 7.5 mm. This duct is surrounded by a concentric flow, which will be referred to as the *pilot flow*, that in reacting conditions enables the injection of hot combustion products to stabilise the flame. The pilot flow is surrounded by a co-flow of air. Note that in the configuration investigated here, the air co-flow is assumed to extend over the entire bottom boundary of the domain. In experimental setups, the co-flow is often injected through a smaller annular duct. The spray flame is assumed to be open to the atmosphere on all other sides.

Figure 1: A schematic of the configuration investigated in the present work, which also represents the dimensions of the domain used for large-eddy simulations. A vertical cross section of the domain is shown on the left and the inlet is shown on the right.

When applied, the electric field is generated by a potential difference between two planar electrodes with normal parallel to the axis of the spray duct (the z -axis). One of these electrodes is located at the height of the spray inlet (i.e., $z = 0$ – see Figure 1 for the definition of the coordinate system), whereas the other electrode is located further downstream, sufficiently far from the flame. These electrodes can be practically implemented by means of two metallic grids or perforated plates (e.g., Ref. [14]). The surface of the electrodes is assumed to be sufficiently large to generate a uniform electric field in the entire flame zone, with electric field direction parallel to the axis of the spray duct. The spray is created with charge-injection atomisation, which allows us to obtain charged droplets with a dielectric liquid fuel [15]. The investigated fuel is kerosene, and droplets are assumed to acquire a negative net charge.

Investigated cases

The effect of electrostatic fields on the spray and flow dynamics is investigated in both non-reacting and reacting conditions. The non-reacting ('cold flow') cases allow the effect of the electric fields on the trajectory of droplets and spray jet dynamics to be studied without the additional complexity of chemical reactions; the reacting cases build on the knowledge developed from the cold flow conditions and allow us to identify the effect of a reacting mixture and an increase in the temperature of the jet on the lifetime of the droplets under electric forces. The investigated cases are summarised in Table 1. The pilot flow is pure air (at the same temperature as the other air flows) for the cold flow simulations, whereas for the reacting cases the pilot consists of a mixture of combustion products (mass composition: $Y_{CO_2} = 0.104$, $Y_{H_2O} = 0.209$, $Y_{N_2} = 0.687$) at high temperature. The behaviour of the system is assessed for different strengths of the electrostatic field; electrostatic fields pointing both upwards (positive z -direction) and downwards are investigated. Since the droplets are negatively charged, an upward electric field results in a downward electric force on the droplets. A monodisperse spray is assumed with droplet diameter at injection equal to $d_0 = 50 \mu\text{m}$ and a mass flow rate of 0.03 g/s , which corresponds to a stoichiometric air-fuel ratio in the spray jet. Droplets are injected at the same temperature and same velocity as the air flow. The charge of the droplets is assumed to be half of the Rayleigh stability limit [7], which can be considered as an upper limit after atomisation, as suggested by experiments [16].

Table 1: Investigated conditions: U_j is the bulk velocity of the jet; U_{cf} is the velocity of the co-flow; U_p is the velocity of the pilot flow; \dot{m}_f indicates the mass flow rate of the spray; T_{air} and T_p are the temperatures of the air flows and pilot flow, respectively; E_z is the z -component of the electric field.

Case	U_j (m/s)	U_{cf} (m/s)	U_p (m/s)	\dot{m}_f (g/s)	T_{air} (K)	T_p (K)	E_z (kV/m)
Non-react.	8.17	0.5	3.7	0.03	293	293	{-100, 0, 50, 100}
Reacting	8.17	0.1	3.7	0.03	293	2226	{-100, 0, 50, 100}

Large-eddy simulations

Simulations are performed using the large-eddy simulation approach and a two-way coupled Eulerian-Lagrangian method for dilute sprays. The method is the same as used in previous work [5] with the addition of chemical source terms and combustion modelling. Droplets are modelled as spherical particles with gravity, drag and electric forces acting on them. All other forces are neglected. The electric field is computed from the solution of the electrostatic potential. Local variations of the electrostatic potential due to the presence of charge droplets as well as repulsion forces between charged droplets are neglected in this study. Evaporation is modelled with a rapid mixing model, with Ranz-Marshall correlation for heat transfer [17]. Since the focus of this work is on the effect of spray location on the global characteristics of the flame, combustion is simply modelled as infinitely fast chemistry. A single-step chemical mechanism is used, with water and carbon dioxide being the only combustion products. Note that the formation of charged species, such as radicals and ionic species, is not included in the chemical mechanism. Therefore, it is not possible to capture the effects of the electric field on the movement of gaseous species and related ionic wind effects [18]. The use of more comprehensive chemical mechanisms that include the formation of ionic species and free electrons, as well as intermediate species, should be addressed in future studies. Depending on the chosen combustion model and simulation framework, closure of terms in the transport equations representing sub-grid effects of electric fields may be necessary.

Numerical setup

The numerical domain, shown in Fig. 1, is a cylindrical geometry concentric with the axis of the spray duct and includes the region downstream of the exit of the spray jet. The inlet velocity of the air flow in the spray jet is modelled with a power-law profile ($u_z = U_0(1 - r/R)^{1/7}$, where U_0 is the velocity at the centre of the air flow, r is the radial distance from the centre of the airflow and R is the radius of the spray jet inlet). In contrast, a uniform velocity is used for both the pilot flow and the air co-flow. No turbulent fluctuations are imposed at any of the air inlets. The lateral boundary is modelled with a slip condition, and a wave transmissive condition is used for the pressure at the outlet. Species composition and temperature are imposed at all inlets. For the electrostatic potential, a potential difference between the bottom and top boundaries of the domain is imposed. The bottom of the domain is assumed to be grounded (zero potential), whereas the value of the potential on the top part of the domain (outlet boundary) is adjusted to obtain the desired external electric field ($|\mathbf{E}| = \Delta\phi/L$, where \mathbf{E} is the electric field, ϕ is the electric potential and L is the distance between the top and bottom boundaries). The domain is discretized with a hexahedral grid of about 4.9 million cells. Refinements are used near the inlets and shear layers between the three concentric flows. Second-order spatial discretization schemes are used for all quantities and a first-order Euler scheme is used for the discretization in time. The timestep (of the order of 10^{-6} s) was adjusted to keep the maximum CFL number lower than 0.4. For the computation of statistics (time averages and root mean square deviations), averages in non-reacting and reacting cases are performed for 0.1 s and 0.5 s, respectively.

Figure 2: The z -component of the jet velocity (a-d) and the cloud of charged droplets (e-h), coloured by age, overlaid on the z -component of the jet velocity after 200 ms from the beginning of droplet injection. The velocity fields are shown on a plane normal to the x -direction passing through the centre of the domain. Results for different electric fields are reported as indicated by the annotation at the top of the figure.

Results

The velocity field and spray location obtained with cold flow simulations are first presented, to assess the effect of an electric field in the absence of a flame. Then, reacting conditions are analysed with a focus on vapour distribution and flame location.

Cold-flow simulations

Figure 2 shows an instantaneous snapshot of the z -component of the velocity and the droplets in the spray for the four electric fields investigated in this work. The age of the droplets is also indicated, to visualise their residence time in the domain after injection. The air flow injected through the spray inlet shows the typical features observed for jets with relatively high injection velocity. The air jet penetrates up to about one third of the domain before it breaks up with substantial formation of turbulent structures. In the absence of an electric field, the droplets carried by the air flow follow the evolution of the air flow. The droplets show a vertical coherent motion in the region immediately downstream of the injection plane. Then as the air jet develops into turbulent structures, the droplet locations become more dispersed. The relatively small diameters of the droplets imply short relaxation times; therefore, the droplets tend to follow the air flow with a small relative velocity and exit the domain a long time after injection. If an electric field is applied in the positive z -direction (electric forces on the droplets in the negative z -direction), the penetration of the droplets is reduced. The spray penetrates up to a maximum height without reaching the outlet boundary of the domain. With an electric field of $E_z = 50$ kV/m, droplets in the centre of the jet (where the flow velocity is maximum)

Figure 3: The z -component of the velocity time averaged over 100 ms along a line passing through the centre of the domain in the z -direction. Each line corresponds to each of the four cases investigated in Figure 2.

tend to stabilise at an intermediate height. This is demonstrated by the large age of droplets located at the tip of the spray cloud. Note that droplets located on the outer part of the spray tend to experience a lower air flow velocity, which implies lower drag forces. For a given droplet diameter and the same net charge, the electric field strength necessary to stabilise the droplets (i.e., zero absolute velocity along z) is a function of the gas phase velocity [7]. This implies that for the selected electric field, stabilisation of droplets can be achieved only for those droplets in a region of the flow where the air velocity allows for a balance between drag and electric forces. If the air velocity is too small, the electric force becomes dominant and a reverse flow of droplets is observed. This is the case for droplets in the outer part of the spray that tend to move back towards the inlet plane (see the droplets with large age close to the inlet for $E_z = 50$ kV/m in Figure 2(f)). If the strength of the electric field is further increased, e.g., case with $E_z = 100$ kV/m, the droplet trajectory is completely reversed and the droplets quickly reach the inlet plane after an initial transient due to the vertical upward injection velocity. In practical situations (e.g., a cold start), this situation should be avoided since it leads to the entrainment of liquid fuel into the air flows, or the wetting of the base plates (if present) with fuel. Therefore, modulation of the strength of the electric field may be necessary during ignition transients. If the electric forces are in the same direction as the air jet flow, then the spray quickly penetrates and leaves the domain as demonstrated by the case with $E_z = -100$ kV/m in Figure 2. With $E_z = -100$ kV/m, the spray tends to stay coherent with little dispersion of the cloud for the entire height of the domain. This is due to the strong vertical acceleration of the droplets induced by the electric forces, which are dominant over the drag.

It is also interesting to investigate the effect of the droplets on the spray air flow. Considering the cases with electric field in the positive z -direction, an increase in the strength of the electric field leads to an increase in the momentum exchange between the droplets and the air flow. The stronger the electric field, the higher the relative velocity of the droplets with respect to the air flow (with some droplets moving in the opposite direction). This leads to an increase of loss of momentum of the air, which results in an earlier formation of turbulent structures (see top row in Figure 2) and a lower penetration of the air jet, as demonstrated in Figure 3 by the time average of the z -component of the velocity along the centreline of the domain. On the contrary, for electric forces in the same direction of the air jet, there is a transfer of momentum from the droplets to the air flow, which increases the speed of the air jet. Note that the presence of external electric forces generally increases the relative velocity between the the droplets and

Figure 4: The temperature (a-d), the z -component of the velocity (e-h) and an enlarged view of the charged droplets (i-l), coloured by age, overlaid on the mass fraction of fuel, Y_f , at time $t = 1$ s after injection. The region shown in (i-l) aligns with the dashed square of length 0.112 m marked on (a). The dotted square of length 0.3 m indicates the region visualised in Figure 5. All values are shown on a plane normal to the x -direction passing through the centre of the domain. Results for different electric fields are reported as indicated by the annotation at the top of the figure.

the carrier phase [19], which further enhances the two-way coupled characteristics of the spray flow. The understanding and quantification of these effects is crucial to achieve full control of the droplet location in the burner.

Flame simulations

Instantaneous snapshots of the temperature field and z -component of the velocity field are shown in Figure 4, together with the location of the spray and age of the droplets. Results for different electric fields are reported. All cases show the formation of a relatively compact

Figure 5: The statistics of the time average of the temperature (a-d), the mass fraction of fuel (e-h) and the mass fraction of CO₂ (i-l). Each panel shows the time average on the left, which is denoted by $\bar{}$, and the root mean square deviation (RMS) on the right, which is denoted by \prime . All values are shown on a plane normal to the x -direction passing through the centre of the domain. The area shown in each panel corresponds to the square of length 0.3 m indicated in Figure 4(a) (dotted line). Results for different electric fields are reported as indicated by the annotation at the top of the figure.

flame. The flow tends to be laminar close to the spray jet inlet, with turbulent structures developing at the tip of the high-temperature region. This behaviour is typical of spray flames under the investigated conditions and is not commented on further. Instead, we want to focus on the spray behaviour under different electric fields and its effects on the flame characteristics. As demonstrated in Figure 4, the spray fully evaporates in a region very close to the injection plane (within $z = 0.1$ m), which is a consequence of the high evaporation rates induced by the high flame temperature. All droplets fully evaporate in less than 10 ms after injection. Looking more in detail at the spray penetration, observations similar to those made for the cold flow

also apply to the reacting cases. For electric fields in the positive z -direction (electric forces on the droplets in the negative z -direction), the penetration of the spray decreases with increasing strength of the electric field. Due to the very short evaporation time, no reverse flow of the droplets is observed for all investigated conditions. When the applied electric field is in the opposite direction (electric forces on the droplets in the positive z -direction), the droplets tend to reach the flame region quicker (with a smaller age compared to the case with no applied electric field). However, the spray penetration does not change substantially. This can be explained as follows: as the droplets tend to move closer and closer to the reacting region, the increase in temperature of the carrier phase further enhances the evaporation rate with droplets completing their evaporation before reaching farther heights.

The change in penetration of the spray affects the location of vapour release, altering the extent of the reacting region. This is shown in Figure 5 by means of the time-averaged fields of temperature, fuel and CO₂ mass fractions and their RMS values. For the cases with the electric field in the positive z -direction, the reacting layer (the areas close to the inlet with high temperature gradients and high RMS values of the temperature) moves closer to the injection plane with increasing strength of the electric field. This is a consequence of the more compact spray penetration and the release of fuel vapour closer to the spray inlet, as demonstrated by the time-averaged fuel mass fraction. The mass fraction of carbon dioxide follows the same trend observed for the temperature fields. Relatively large fluctuations of all quantities are observed in a narrow region of conical shape close to the spray injection plane, which corresponds to the reacting layer, as well as in the post flame region, where turbulent structures develop.

Discussion

The present investigation demonstrates that with realistic electric fields, largely below the breakdown threshold for air (around 3 MV/m at ambient temperature), it is possible to change the spray location, with implications on the fuel vapour distribution and the flame length. The penetration of the spray can be controlled by modulating the strength and direction of the electric field, which may increase the operating range of novel hybrid thermal-electric combustion technologies. If state-of-the-art charge injection atomisers are used [16], the net charge in each droplet can also be controlled within a range, further extending the parameter space for control.

A monodisperse spray with the same net charge for all droplets has been considered in this work. The presence of a polydisperse spray with a relatively wide droplet size distribution, together with differences in net charge between droplets, may make the control of the spray trajectory and location more challenging. Large differences in droplet diameters have an impact on drag forces, whereas the net charge affects the electric force. Large dispersions of either of these parameters makes it more difficult to achieve a balance between drag and electric forces such that the penetration of the entire spray is controlled. The control of sprays characterised by a dispersion of droplet size and net charge should be investigated in future work.

The achievement of modulation of the spray location is strongly dependent on the spray jet bulk velocity. To keep the electric field below the breakdown threshold of air, relatively low velocities must be employed (otherwise, the drag force cannot be counterbalanced by the electric force). In addition, in reacting conditions the total evaporation time of droplets significantly reduces, which limits the time frame available to modify the trajectories of the droplets. In principle, the shorter the evaporation time, the stronger the external forces must be to induce significant changes in the trajectories of the droplets.

It is reminded that in this study charged species and free electrons formed during the combustion process are assumed to be negligible. This is a strong assumption since there is plenty of evidence that the combustion of hydrocarbons leads to substantial formation of ionic species (e.g., [18]). The movement of charged gaseous species under an electric field and their collisions with neutral species could generate a relatively strong bulk movement of the flow, known as ionic wind, which could further contribute to the change in shape of the flame. Integration of a detailed chemical mechanism that includes free electrons and ionic species [18], as

well as development of a large-eddy simulation framework with closure of sub-grid scale terms representing the effect of species drift induced by electric fields are part of current research. Additionally, combustion has been modelled with a simple approach in this work. Investigation of spray flames with a higher level of turbulence will require the use of more advanced combustion models [20].

Concluding remarks

The use of electrostatic forces to modulate the penetration of charged droplets in a spray jet flame configuration and the related effects on the fuel distribution and flame shape have been investigated using large-eddy simulations. Results demonstrate that external electric fields offer the possibility of controlling the location of the droplets. When the applied electric field exerts a force on the charged droplets in the opposite direction to the spray jet flow, the penetration of the spray decreases with increasing strength of the electric field. This results in a more compact reacting region that moves closer to the spray inlet. When the applied electric field is in the opposite direction, the electric field tends to move the droplets far away from the spray inlet, an effect that is very evident in cold flow conditions; in reacting conditions, however, the related changes on both the fuel vapour distribution and the temperature field are less evident. The present investigation provides evidence that electrostatic fields have the potential of assisting fuel preparation by reducing the space necessary for full evaporation, an effect that could be used to build compact combustors with fuel flexibility enabled by modulation of the strength of the applied electric fields.

Acknowledgements

This work was performed within the framework of the FFLECS Project funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101096436. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. UK participants in Horizon Europe Project FFLECS are supported by UKRI grant numbers 10101902 (Imperial College London) and 10085576 (University of Cambridge).

We acknowledge computational resources and support provided by the Imperial College Research Computing Service (doi.org/10.14469/hpc/2232). We also acknowledge William A. Liljeland and Francesco Merloni who contributed to develop know-how on the spray jet flame configuration investigated here with their final year projects at Imperial.

References

- [1] Ritchie, H., "Sector by sector: where do global greenhouse gas emissions come from?", *Our World in Data* (2020), <https://ourworldindata.org/ghg-emissions-by-sector>.
- [2] Yue, M., Lambert, H., Pahon, E., Roche, R., Jemei, S., Hissel, D., "Hydrogen energy systems: A critical review of technologies, applications, trends and challenges", *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 146: 111180 (2021).
- [3] Pereirinha, P.G., González, M., Carrilero, I., Anseán, D., Alonso, J., Viera, J.C., "Main trends and challenges in road transportation electrification", *Transportation Research Procedia* 33: 235–242 (2018), XIII Conference on Transport Engineering, CIT2018.
- [4] Brelje, B.J., Martins, J.R., "Electric, hybrid, and turboelectric fixed-wing aircraft: A review of concepts, models, and design approaches", *Progress in Aerospace Sciences* 104: 1–19 (2019).

- [5] Fredrich, D., Weiland, E., Giusti, A., “Electrostatic fields for the control of evaporating charged fuel sprays”, *International Journal of Multiphase Flow* 160: 104312 (2023).
- [6] Sakhrieh, A., Lins, G., Dinkelacker, F., Hammer, T., Leipertz, A., Branston, D., “The influence of pressure on the control of premixed turbulent flames using an electric field”, *Combustion and Flame* 143(3): 313–322 (2005).
- [7] Giusti, A., Fredrich, D., “Fuel effects on the electrostatic control of charged droplet trajectories”, *Fuel* 366: 131009 (2024).
- [8] Marcum, S., Ganguly, B., “Electric-field-induced flame speed modification”, *Combustion and Flame* 143(1): 27–36 (2005).
- [9] Saito, M., Arai, T., Arai, M., “Control of soot emitted from acetylene diffusion flames by applying an electric field”, *Combustion and Flame* 119(3): 356–366 (1999).
- [10] van den Boom, J., Konnov, A., Verhasselt, A., Kornilov, V., de Goey, L., Nijmeijer, H., “The effect of a dc electric field on the laminar burning velocity of premixed methane/air flames”, *Proceedings of the Combustion Institute* 32(1): 1237–1244 (2009).
- [11] Altendorfner, F., Kuhl, J., Zigan, L., Leipertz, A., “Study of the influence of electric fields on flames using planar lif and piv techniques”, *Proceedings of the Combustion Institute* 33(2): 3195–3201 (2011).
- [12] Ahmed, T., Kourmatzis, A., Singh, G., Masri, A.R., “Turbulent spray flames of kerosene issuing from a hybrid electrohydrodynamic-air-blast atomiser”, *Combustion and Flame* 239: 111573 (2022), a dedication to Professor Kenneth Noel Corbett Bray.
- [13] Gounder, J.D., Kourmatzis, A., Masri, A.R., “Turbulent piloted dilute spray flames: Flow fields and droplet dynamics”, *Combustion and Flame* 159(11): 3372–3397 (2012).
- [14] Park, D.G., Chung, S.H., Cha, M.S., “Bidirectional ionic wind in nonpremixed counter-flow flames with dc electric fields”, *Combustion and Flame* 168: 138–146 (2016).
- [15] Shrimpton, J., Yule, A., “Characterisation of charged hydrocarbon sprays for application in combustion systems”, *Experiments in Fluids* 26: 460–469 (1999).
- [16] Rigit, A.R.H., Shrimpton, J.S., “Estimation of the diameter–charge distribution in polydisperse electrically charged sprays of electrically insulating liquids”, *Experiments in Fluids* 46: 1159–1171 (2009).
- [17] Miller, R., Harstad, K., Bellan, J., “Evaluation of equilibrium and non-equilibrium evaporation models for many-droplet gas-liquid flow simulations”, *International Journal of Multiphase Flow* 24(6): 1025–1055 (1998).
- [18] Belhi, M., Lee, B.J., Cha, M.S., Im, H.G., “Three-dimensional simulation of ionic wind in a laminar premixed bunsen flame subjected to a transverse dc electric field”, *Combustion and Flame* 202: 90–106 (2019).
- [19] Weiland, E., Giusti, A., “Turbulent dispersion and evaporation of charged nanofuel droplet clouds under the influence of electrostatic fields”, *International Journal of Spray and Combustion Dynamics* 16(4): 269–289 (2024).
- [20] Giusti, A., Mastorakos, E., “Turbulent combustion modelling and experiments: Recent trends and developments”, *Flow Turbulence and Combustion* 103: 874–869 (2019).